

PROPOSED LAW or Ordinance

Title: Institutionalizing Survey Process to be Conducted by Local COMELEC

Goal: Ensure the Integrity of the Surveys

Private survey firms such as SWS and Pulse Asia don't publicize who sponsored every survey and for how much budget. Result of survey can influence the mind of some Filipinos regarding important issues, as well as voter preference in both national and local election.

Conducting a national survey can be very costly. We do not know how many of their employee conduct surveys in every part of the Philippines or whether each barangay and city is represented. We also don't know how survey firms select the people to be surveyed. There is no transparency mechanism for the selection process of specific people to survey.

Additionally, it is unclear whether the selection process is random or, if it is, how random it truly is. Important issues about conducting survey:

- Do they survey students, tambay, Filipino worker, registered voter, etc...? What if the person selected to be surveyed is not available in their house, what are they going to do?
- Who collect and tabulate the final results? The COMELEC as a constitutionally independent body should have a copy of the individual survey result for verification and audit.

The late former Senator Miriam Defensor Santiago said before "Kung susundin natin ang kagustuhan ng survey firm, they will be the one to choose our next leaders. Our right to vote will be forfeited in their favor. Sila ngayon ang magiging kingmaker niyan. Hindi naman pwede yun."

Proposal #1:

Some surveys of SWS and Pulse Asia have at least 2000 people as *sample* of the entire population. I think, at least 10% of this sample should be audited by COMELEC or any independent body. The COMELEC should have the copy of the 2000 sample, then they can randomly choose 10% from it. The local COMELEC can go to this people to redo again the survey and compare to the first result of the SWS and Pulse Asia. This can improve and ensure the integrity of the survey.

Local surveys are also important for local politicians and local issues.

Proposal #2:

Institutionalize the conduct of local survey in the entire Philippines.

The local COMELEC has the manpower, data on registered voters, and the resources to conduct local surveys. They are highly independent, with salaries automatically provided to them, without the influence of any politicians or private individuals. The local COMELEC is also scattered throughout the Philippines.

Step 1: The City Local COMELEC uploads the list of registered voters on their official FB page.

Step 2: The City Local Head shall randomly choose at least 500 people as a sample to be surveyed.

Through FB Live, the selection process must be open and public to avoid irregularities. Prorate the sample based on the number of registered voters in each barangay.

At least two drinking transparent glass.

- First glass: Name of barangays in a City
- Second glass: The maximum number of registered voters in a barangay.
- Randomly choose first barangay in the first glass, and the number in the second glass. That person will be surveyed by the local COMELEC in a City.

There are 149 cities in the Philippines.

149 cities x 500 people = 74,500 people can be surveyed instead of 2000 in private firms (SWS and Pulse Asia).

500 people in every city can be changed to 10% or any number based on the available local or national budget.

Some cities with an annual budget of more than one billion can conduct their local surveys based on the two-step proposal above. Local surveys are very important for local politicians and local issues.

Even though it is a local survey, including preferences for national positions is a must, such as surveys for the President, Vice President, and Senators, as well as important national issues like the West Philippine Sea.

Note: This is not a proper law or ordinance. But the core concepts are all here.

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